

**Warning and Mitigation Technologies
for Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances
Effects**

TechTIDE

D3.4

**Methodology for the identification of the
interhemispheric circulation**

Version 1.1

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Abstract

In order to obtain quantitative information on the likeliness and morphology of interhemispheric circulation of Large-Scale Traveling Ionospheric Disturbances (LSTID) we examined 38 event periods lasting between 8 and 24 hours each during which LSTID were observed according to the TID occurrence list prepared by WP3. These periods coincided, with four exceptions, with geomagnetic storms covering the time from the ssc until well into the recovery phase. We used exclusively GPS based detection methods, specifically information on Total Electron Content (TEC), TEC deviations in space and time from a background reference (dTEC), and the Rate Of TEC change in time (ROT), all inferred from GPS receiver networks in Europe and Africa. In 13 out of the 38 time periods we got sufficient data coverage to identify potential occurrence of LSTID in both hemispheres.

Our analysis reveals that TID were always hemispherically conjugate, that is, TID were either not detected at all (1 event period) or else seen in both hemispheres simultaneously (12 event periods), irrespective of their auroral or equatorial launch regions. However, interhemispheric circulation (propagation of a TID from one hemisphere across the equator into the other hemisphere) was detected in only 3 out of the 13 cases. Under the constraint that our data sample was heavily biased toward geomagnetic storm time events we conclude that hemispheric conjugacy of LSTID is highly probable while interhemispheric circulation rather unlikely but still occurring during some periods.

We also examined geomagnetic indices (the Dst and SYM-H storm-time indices, the IL and IU local Scandinavian auroral electrojet indices, and the northern and southern Polar Cap indices PCN and PCS). We found that the enhancements of the auroral electrojet and polar cap indices could reach high values during the TID time periods, but there was in general no clear temporal coincidence between increasing magnitude of indices and launch of TID. We conclude that the magnitude of geomagnetic indices may in a statistical sense be related to the occurrence rate of TID (as was reported in the literature), but the uncertainty remains large. Geomagnetic indices appear to be less suitable for precise direct prediction of TID occurrence but may be useful as supplementary information.

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Executive Summary

The objective of the study which led to this report is an examination of interhemispheric occurrence characteristics of Large-Scale Traveling Ionospheric Disturbances (LSTID). The TID considered in the TechTIDE project have (i) different spatial and temporal scales (large scale and medium scale), and (ii) different source mechanism, ranging from tropospheric to magnetospheric-ionospheric perturbations in the auroral zones and near the equator. Here we consider LSTID with magnetospheric-ionospheric excitation mechanism, taken from the list of TID occurrences compiled within Work Package 3. Neither did we consider the detailed nature of the physical processes which led to the TID nor did we distinguish TID according to intensity, we rather employed a binary (yes/no) assessment of occurrence.

We examined 38 event periods the vast majority of which occurred during geomagnetic storms. During these periods the TID were launched at auroral latitudes, equatorial latitudes, or both. For detection and characterisation we relied entirely on GPS products from ground-based receivers in Europe and South Africa. The GPS products include Total Electron Content (TEC), deviations of TEC from a reference background (dTEC) and the temporal change of TEC (Rate of TEC, ROT). We further considered the global geomagnetic storm indices Dst and SYM-H, the local Scandinavian auroral electrojet indices IL and IU, and the northern and southern Polar Cap indices PCN and PCS.

We address two principal questions, namely (i) what is the likeliness that LSTID occur simultaneously in both hemispheres (hemispheric conjugacy), and (ii) what is the likeliness that LSTID launched in one hemisphere propagate across the equator into the other hemisphere (interhemispheric circulation). A third question concerns the likeliness of a causal relation between LSTID occurrence and variations of the geomagnetic indices. Our answers to these questions are as follows:

- (1) In all 13 time periods (out of 38) with sufficient data coverage in both hemispheres we detected hemispherically conjugate TID occurrence.
- (2) In only 3 out of those 13 time periods we detected interhemispheric circulation.
- (3) Based on an examination of individual cases we cannot conclude that the occurrence of TID and their interhemispheric circulation is significantly correlated with the magnitude or rate of temporal change of geomagnetic indices.

Our message to operators who rely on communication and navigation using radio waves is the following:

- ◆ During geomagnetic storms the likeliness of TID occurrence is high.
- ◆ If TID are launched in one hemisphere it is almost certain that TID are also launched in the other hemisphere.

1. Research background

1.1. Equatorward and poleward propagating large-scale traveling thermospheric and ionospheric disturbances – recent studies

It is widely accepted that auroral substorms constitute a prime source for the generation of Atmospheric Gravity Waves (AGW) and their ionospheric manifestations, Traveling Ionospheric Disturbances (TID) (e.g., Hocke & Schlegel, 1996). The driver in the auroral zone appears to be the variability of the auroral electrojet which is largest after substorm onset. While medium-scale TID (MSTID) tend to have a short life time and propagate over short distances before their energy is dissipated, large-scale TID (LSTID) were observed to travel over long distances (thousands of kilometres) and may even make a full Earth orbit (Bowman & Mortimer, 2011, Guo et al., 2015). Ding et al. (2008) studied a large number of LSTID and reported their peak occurrence to occur at local times consistent with their generation in the auroral zone and subsequent travel over one pole or even both poles to their midlatitude observing sites. They further point out that the statistical occurrence rate of storm-time LSTID launched at high latitudes increases with increasing AE index. Nevertheless, about 10% of LSTID occurred during relatively quiet times ($AE < 400$ nT). The statistical relationship between LSTID occurrence rate and AE index shows a broad variance. Valladares et al. (2009) analysed TEC obtained from 263 GPS receivers in North and South America operating during the Halloween storm. They observed equatorward propagating LSTID over periods of several hours during one of which AE was as small as 500 nT and as large as 4000 nT in the other.

A second source, besides substorms, are magnetospheric storms. Both are characterised by enhanced geomagnetic activity, but the former provides energy to TID from the auroral electrojets while the latter involves also the equatorial electrojet. The generation mechanisms are different. But both source processes can generate TID at the same time. In fact, LSTID, which have likely been generated concurrently in the auroral zones and near the geomagnetic equator, were observed after the onset of a geomagnetic storm, with the auroral electrojets responsible for equatorward propagating TID and the equatorial electrojet for poleward traveling TID (Habarulema et al., 2015, 2016).

A small number of case studies of interhemispheric circulation of AGW and TID were published in recent years. All of them discuss observations taken during geomagnetic storms accompanied by intense substorm activity.

Guo et al. (2014) analysed CHAMP observations of neutral air density at 400 km altitude during the Halloween storm and observed nightside AGW in both hemispheres, triggered by an interplanetary shock, with strong amplitude enhancement at the magnetic equator. They interpret the enhancement as constructive interference between two AGW traveling equatorward from both hemispheres. Such interference, if it happens, will likely have an impact also on the TID amplitudes. In a subsequent study Guo et al. (2015) analysed neutral air density variations observed with CHAMP and GRACE at 400 km altitude during a moderate storm. They report equatorward propagating AGW which appear to exhibit amplitude enhancements at the geomagnetic equator concurrently on the day and night sides.

Several studies addressed directly TID rather than AGW occurrence. Pradipta et al. (2016) examined TEC data and ionograms collected during a strong geomagnetic storm. They observed TID coming from the auroral zones and propagating from the North and South American sectors toward the geomagnetic equator where the amplitudes appeared to become enhanced and exceeded the sum of those arriving from both hemispheres. The observations do not unambiguously demonstrate a TID propagation from one hemisphere across the geomagnetic equator into the other hemisphere. Borries et al. (2016) analysed

Total Electron Content (TEC) inferred from GNSS observations in the European-African longitude sector during the Saint Patrick's Day storm and found TID propagating equatorward simultaneously in the northern and southern hemispheres. Valladares et al (2009) investigated TEC observations made over North and South America. The identified TID around local noon propagating towards the geographic equator where they arrived at the same time, but no further propagation into the opposite hemisphere was detected. It seems as if in that case TEC perturbations interacted destructively.

2. Analysis method

2.1. Characteristics of the TID data sets

We examined a total of 38 event periods lasting from 8 to 24 hours each, with the objective to identify and track LSTID in the European-African sector constrained by the +70 to -40 deg geographic latitude and 15 to 40 deg E geographic longitude contours. With 'event period' we denote time intervals during which one or more events (i.e., TID) occurred. Figure 1 shows the locations of GNSS, digisonde and HF Doppler sounders in Europe and Africa.

Figure 1: Sites where instruments are located which are used within the TechTIDE project.

Blue dots: Digisondes (not all were fully operational at the time of writing this report).

Red dot groups: HF Doppler sounder systems.

Green dots: GPS receivers of the IGS, UNAVCO and TrigNet GNSS networks. Note that stations are sparse in the Sahara zone and practically absent in the sub-Saharan zone.

Dotted line across Africa: geomagnetic equator.

The event periods were all taken from the sample events list initiated by the WP3 leader and subsequently filled with notes and data with support from other TechTIDE consortium members. The list specifies days and fractions of days during which TID occurrence had been reported respectively detected using methods adopted by the

TechTIDE project. The methods employed include the TEC gradient, HF-TID, and HF interferometry methods. The data coverage was not equal for all event periods, GNSS data availability over Africa was sparse for the more recent events (i.e., for most of the year 2017).

The WP3 TID list includes a few cases of MSTID with tropospheric sources. But the vast majority of the events are TID with geomagnetic triggers. We use the term 'event' for a single LSTID or a group of LSTID observed at some time during the event period. The events occurred during geomagnetic storms of varying intensity, ranging from moderate to superstorms, caused by Coronal Mass Ejections (CME) with or without associated solar flares, Corotating Interaction Regions (CIR), High Speed Streams emanating from Coronal Holes (CH HSS), or Solar Sector Boundary Crossings (SSBC).

In order to achieve our task we employed exclusively TEC data products (TEC, dTEC, and ROT) of LSTID observations. TEC was derived using the IGS, UNAVCO, and TrigNet networks of ground-based GNSS receivers in Europe and Africa and is given in TECU ($1 \text{ TECU} = 10^{16} \text{ el/m}^2$). dTEC is the difference between unsmoothed TEC observations and a TEC reference level specified as a 1-hour running mean of the unsmoothed data (DLR) or polynomial smoothing (SANS). ROT (Rate Of TEC) is the temporal TEC derivative given in TECU/min. TEC gradients (spatial TEC derivatives) are also available for some of the event periods but were not considered. They are primarily indicative of the AGW-LSTID source region and excitation process and not particularly important for the purpose of this report. The reasons for concentrating on TEC data products were threefold.

- (1) Many GNSS receivers are operating routinely in large areas of Europe and Africa, with the exception of the sub-Sahara zone, and can deliver reasonably homogeneous data sets for all events studied.
- (2) Digisonde based methods (HF-TID and HF interferometry) require coordinated measurements from at least three digisondes in both Europe and South Africa. At this early stage of the project the technical conditions for operating digisondes as required for using these methods were not always fulfilled.
- (3) Digisondes are not deployed in equatorial Africa, hence the equatorial region which is important to our study is not covered.

2.2 Detection of large-scale ionospheric disturbances in GPS TEC data products

For this study we examined TEC, dTEC and ROT maps. Not all of the three map types were available for all periods examined. In several cases the types available were not the same for the European and African regions. ROT and dTEC maps turned out to be the most useful products for this study. The dTEC magnitude did not exceed ± 3 TECU in the events we examined while daytime TEC at low and equatorial latitudes reached in many cases several tens of TECU and would thus render small variations nearly invisible. This necessitated in many cases combining a dTEC map from one hemisphere and a ROT map from the other hemisphere in order to obtain a synoptic view of LSTID occurrence.

We demonstrate the combined use of dTEC and ROT maps using as an example an event of 08 March 2012 (see the time-latitude diagram in Figure 2). The event took place when the magnetosphere recovered from a moderate geomagnetic storm (min Dst=-88 nT). The perturbation started with the magnetosphere encountering an interplanetary shock which compressed it and drove Dst briefly up to +22 nT. A few hours later a strong storm started (min Dst=-145 nT).

The three panels of Figure 2 are synchronised in time. They all start at 10 UT and end at 22 UT. The spacing between latitude tick marks is the same in all three panels. The top panel shows dTEC (provided by DLR), the middle panel ROT (provided by DLR) and the bottom ROT (provided by SANSA). Here ROT (Rate of TEC) is simplified to the term TEC Rate which means the same as ROT.

One notices in the top panel a nearly 1-hour lasting TEC enhancement with an amplitude of ~ 1 TECU above the background. The event was launched in the northern hemisphere auroral oval shortly after 13 UT and subsequently propagated equatorward to reach 30 deg latitude at ~ 15.30 UT. The dotted line between 50 deg and 30 deg northern latitude traces the peak of the TEC enhancement. The same dotted line, placed exactly at the same time-latitude points, is also shown in the middle and bottom panels.

If one observes a temporary TEC enhancement (positive dTEC) one expects to see positive ROT values prior to the peak enhancement and negative ROT values after it. This is indeed seen in the middle and bottom panels. During the hours preceding the peak of the TEC enhancement (indicated by the dotted line) the TEC rate (i.e., ROT) is positive and in the hours succeeding the peak negative. We consider this a justification for our approach to infer temporally constrained TEC enhancements from either dTEC or ROT, making use of the positive/negative sequence of ROT (or else negative/positive in case of negative dTEC) to mark the positive (or negative) dTEC peak.

2.3 Supporting data

In order to relate the LSTID observations to magnetospheric and ionospheric background conditions we expect to rely on established indices and indicators, among them SYM-H (a geomagnetic storm intensity index), PCN and PCS (northern and southern polar cap indices, frequently used as proxies for the solar wind - magnetosphere merging electric field), local European sector auroral electrojet indices IU and IL (upper and lower extrema of geomagnetic field variations recorded by the Scandinavian IMAGE magnetometer array), and the AATR indicator (one of the TID identification methodologies adopted by the TechTIDE project) from one South African and three European sites. Note that no global or local auroral electrojet indices exist for the southern hemisphere. It is due to the fact that the latitudes of interest (roughly 60 to 70 deg southern geomagnetic latitude) coincide with oceans which impedes establishment of a sufficient number of geomagnetic observatories.

Dst, PCN, PCS, and AATR are available in near real time (with up to five minutes delay). SYM-H is only published until the end of the preceding month. Full IMAGE network IU and IL indices are published with delays between a few days and one month. The IMAGE PI offered to make available in near real time IU and IL based on the Finnish magnetometer chain rather than the full network. The Finnish chain data will be sufficient for our purpose. The two maps displayed in Figure 3 show the full IMAGE network and the Finnish chain stations.

Details are found at the following websites from where the indices were obtained:

- SYM-H: World Data Center for Geomagnetism Kyoto - Geomagnetic Data Service
<http://wdc.kugi.kyoto-u.ac.jp/aeasy/index.html>
- PCN, PCS: Polar Cap Magnetic Index produced by AARI & DTU
<http://pcindex.org/>
- IL, IU: IMAGE magnetometer array electrojet indicators
http://space.fmi.fi/image/www/index.php?page=il_index
- AATR: Values for hundreds of receivers since December 2013
<http://147.83.27.240/TechTIDE/AATR/data/>

Figure 2: dTEC (top panel) and ROT (middle and bottom panels) on 08 March 2012 over the European-African longitude sector shortly after the arrival of an interplanetary shock.

Figure 3: The complete IMAGE magnetometer network (left panel) and the central longitudinal chain (right panel, red dots).

Source: http://space.fmi.fi/image/verification/Station_selection//Station_selection.html.

Figure 4 shows observations from 17 March 2015 as an example for TID observations (dTEC and ROT in the two uppermost panels) and simultaneous variations of the polar cap indices (PCN and PCS, third panel), the local auroral electrojet indices (IL and IU, fourth panel), and the AATR indicators at one South African and three European sites (bottom panel). This example represents the period of the St. Patrick's day geomagnetic storm on 17 March 2015 which started shortly before 05 UT, had its first moderate SYM-H minimum around 09.30 UT and its major SYM-H minimum at ~23 UT.

In Figure 4 we see four vertical dashed lines. The first line marks the start of excitation of equatorward moving TID at northern latitudes. The time coincides with a decrease of the PCN and PCS indices after having reached a peak, suggesting merging of interplanetary and magnetospheric magnetic fields at the magnetopause 1-2 hours prior to the launch of the TID. The local IL (blue) and IU (red) indices are close to zero, indicating that the auroral electrojets, eastward as well as westward, were still very weak. The second line marks the start of another equatorward propagating TID. It coincides with the intensification of the westward and eastward auroral electrojets as seen in IL and IU, and approximately with a peak of the PCN and PCS indices. We also see substantial negative ROT values at northern and southern low latitudes but not near the geomagnetic equator. The third line marks the start of yet another equatorward propagating TID and the begin of a particularly deep depression of IL (i.e., a sudden enhancement of the westward auroral electrojet). The PCN and PCS indices have been small and positive since several hours and increase only slightly and only after the start of the TID. The fourth line marks yet another start of an equatorward propagating TID. It is accompanied by a peak in the PCN and PCS indices and a substantial IL value (strong westward electrojet).

Figure 4: Equatorward propagating TID observed simultaneously in the northern and southern hemispheres on 17 March 2015. Top panel: dTEC in the northern hemisphere; 2nd panel: ROT in the northern and southern hemispheres; 3rd panel: PCN and PCS; 4th panel: IL and IU; 5th panel: AATR at one southern and three northern hemisphere sites.

This sequence of events is an example of strong enhancements of the magnetopause merging electric field at the start of two TID propagating from the northern auroral zone to the equator. The second, third, and fourth TID fall approximately onto the start of auroral electrojet intensifications. The first TID is neither associated with a large PC index nor with a substantial increase of the IMAGE electrojet indicator.

However, these observations cannot be generalised. We have seen other events where the launch of a TID in the auroral zone and the subsequent equatorward propagation does not correspond to substantial enhancements in PCN or PCS or IL or IU. The event of 07 March 2012, shown in Figure 5, may serve as an example.

Figure 5: Equatorward propagating TID in the northern hemisphere observed on 07 March 2012. Top : dTEC (ordinate: latitude in deg); middle: IL and IU (ordinate: nT); bottom: PCN and PCS (ordinate: mV/m). The abscissa extends from 03 UT to 15 UT in all panels. The vertical dashed lines mark the start of the first and of the last TID.

In this event period the first TID starts shortly after an IL minimum barely exceeding -500 nT and a very weak IU. The last TID with an amplitude twice as large as the first one starts after IU has reached a modest 500 nT and IL is close to zero since several hours. Note that IL and IU not exceeding -400 nT and +400 nT, respectively, are generally considered indicative of weak electrojets. The PCN index does not exceed 6 up to the start of the first TID and reaches a maximum of 9 prior to the start of the last TID.

3. Characteristics of LSTID observed in both hemispheres

In this section we discuss TID observed in both hemispheres under two aspects. First we examine the question whether hemispherically conjugate occurrence of LSTID is the normal situation. With the term 'hemispheric conjugacy' we refer to a simultaneous appearance of equatorward or poleward propagating TID in both hemispheres. For a true conjugacy both must be traveling either equatorward or poleward. Thereafter we examine the question whether it is common that equatorward propagating LSTID cross the equator and enter the opposite hemisphere. We use the term 'interhemispheric circulation' for this type of TID propagation.

3.1 LSTID propagating equatorward but not crossing the equator

We observed many events during geomagnetic storms when LSTID propagated simultaneously from high latitudes in both hemispheres toward the geomagnetic equator but did not penetrate into the opposite hemisphere. Figure 6 shows observations from 02 October 2013 which may serve as an example. The three panels share the same time line, all extend from 08 UT to 20 UT. The latitude spacing is the same in all panels so that a propagation with constant speed will follow a straight line with the same steepness in all panels.

In the top panel we display dTEC (provided by DLR), in the middle panel ROT (provided by DLR) and in the bottom panel also ROT (provided by SANSa). Indicated by a dotted line is an equatorward propagating TID which enters the display field at 08 UT at about 65 deg latitude and exits at 30 deg latitude shortly before 10 UT. In the middle panel we see an identical dotted line, which is placed at the same time-latitude pair, separating positive and negative TEC rates. Its meaning is discussed already in section 2.2 with the help of Figure 2. In the bottom panel we see the same dotted line and along it a separation between positive and negative ROT between 40 and 25 deg before reaching the 20 deg latitude band which is void of observations. After emerging from the observation-free band we cannot detect a continuation of the positive-negative ROT distribution further to the south along the dotted line. Apparently the TID did not travel beyond northern hemisphere low latitudes. Note that in this longitude sector the geomagnetic equator is located at about 10 deg geographic north and in consequence the equatorial ionospheric troughs should be expected at geographic latitudes of about 25 deg N and 5 deg S. The equatorward propagating TID seems to lose its energy in the latitude range of the northern ionospheric trough. Note that local solar time (LST) is about two hours ahead of UT, i.e., 11 UT corresponds to 13 LST.

Date 02 October 2013

Figure 6: TEC (top panel) and ROT (middle and bottom panels) on 02 October 2013 over the European-African longitude sector. The interval starts 1.5 hours after the end of the main phase of a moderate geomagnetic storm ($S\text{YM-H} \approx -90$ nT).

3.2 W-shaped patterns of equatorward and poleward propagating LSTID

We observed on several occasions ROT patterns which resemble in shape the letter 'W' rotated counterclockwise by 90 deg (i.e., placed on its left side). They are seen in Figures 2, 4 and 6 and are repeated here in Figure 7, indicated by white lines tracing the shapes. In the top and bottom panels they appear roughly in the center, in the middle panel close to the left edge.

These W-shaped events share some characteristics which are common to many (but not all) of them. Most were observed close to the equinoxes. The central pivot point of the W shape is found approximately at the geomagnetic equator, the adjacent knee points approximately at the northern and southern equatorial trough locations. The patterns indicate that TID were excited simultaneously at equatorial latitude and high latitudes in both hemispheres. The TID launch at high latitudes appear to have preceded the launch at the equator by a few hours.

Figure 7: W-shaped ROT structures (thin white lines) observed in some TID events.

3.3 LSTID crossing the equator

In Figure 8 we show a first example of a TEC crest and valley sequence of LSTID observed on 22 June 2015 near the summer solstices, 13 hours after the end of the main phase of a severe geomagnetic storm ($\text{SYM-H} \approx -200$ nT) when the recovery phase was well underway. The TID with its origin in the southern hemisphere and propagating northward exhibited a positive dTEC followed by a negative dTEC. A few hours later a TID originating in the northern hemisphere with positive dTEC came into view at low northern latitudes which propagated into the southern hemisphere. They are marked by dotted black arrows in Figure 8. No particular signs of interference at the magnetic equator are noticed.

The TID with positive dTEC came into view at 19 UT at 15 deg south, propagated northward across the equator and exited the field of view at about 22 UT. We do not have data poleward of 40 deg north and sparse data poleward of 15 deg south, so we cannot determine start and end points of the TID propagation. The TID with negative dTEC became visible at 20 UT at 15 deg south, traveled northward with varying speed (i.e., does not follow a straight line in the figure) and exited the field of view at 22.30 UT at 40 deg northern latitude. This TID with negative dTEC is possibly associated with the northward propagating TID with positive dTEC seen one hour earlier. A third TID arrived from the north, entered the field of view at 21 UT at 40 deg latitude, crossed the equator and continued into southern mid-latitudes. It crossed the first northward propagating TID at about 21.30 UT at 30 deg north, without any sign of interference, and the second northward propagating TID at 23 deg north in a latitude band void of TEC data.

As a second example Figure 9 displays TEC observations from 27 March 2017 close to the spring equinox. At equinox we expect that both hemispheres behave approximately identically. Unfortunately the data coverage in the northern hemisphere is limited to a narrow band of only about 15 deg latitude. The data were taken during the main phase of a moderate geomagnetic storm which reached only a $\text{SYM-H} \approx -80$ nT. At about 13 UT one sees a TEC perturbation (dTEC) entering the field of view at 35 deg southern latitude and a faint corresponding TEC crest in the northern hemisphere. A northward propagating TEC crest-valley-crest sequence is seen in the southern hemisphere. The data coverage at ± 10 deg around the geomagnetic equator is poor which makes it difficult to follow the TID. It appears that the same TID are observed after the data gap again in the northern hemisphere (dotted black lines) although no hard confirmation can be offered.

4. Review of TID events

After having pointed out in the previous sections certain specific features of the observed TID by showing representative examples we now turn to an investigation of a larger number of TID observations (and lack of observations in some cases). We selected 38 event periods from the TID list prepared by WP3 for the TechTIDE project. The events span the years 2012 through 2017. As much as possible three types of TEC data products (i.e., TEC, dTEC and ROT) were obtained and subsequently analysed. The TEC products were inferred from GPS network observations made with ground-based receivers located in Europe and Africa.

A summary of all events analysed follows further down in Section 4.1 in the form of a detailed 2-page table.

Figure 8: Equatorward propagating LSTID which enter the opposite hemisphere without any particular sign of interference. Latitude is in geographic degrees. The geomagnetic equator is located at about 10 deg north of the geographic equator.

Figure 9: Northward propagating LSTID coming from the southern hemisphere and crossing the equator. Latitude is in geographic degrees. The geomagnetic equator, with sparse data coverage, is located at about 10 deg north of the geographic equator.

4.1 Synoptic summary table

The next two pages show in tabular form specific characteristics of the events examined for this report. The tables are organised as follows. Each event period occupies one row. Information about the event period is spread over 11 columns with the following entries:

- Col 1: Date of the event period.
- Col 2: Day of the year of the event period.
- Col 3: Time span (begin and end in UT) during which one or more TID were observed in at least one hemisphere. A question mark indicates that a TID could neither be identified nor definitely excluded, mostly because of sparse data coverage.
- Col 4: In case of a geomagnetic storm main phase: minimum of SYM-H index and, separated by a double slash, hours (in UT) of begin and end of the storm main phase; otherwise mention of ssc (with time in UT), recovery phase or storm-free period. Added (-1d) or (+1d) indicate that the given hour refers to the preceding day or the succeeding day, respectively.
- Col 5: Lowest value of the IMAGE electrojet index IL (westward electrojet indicator) and, separated by a double slash, time of its occurrence during the time interval when TID were observed.
- Col 6: Highest value of the IMAGE electrojet index IU (eastward electrojet indicator) and, separated by a double slash, time of its occurrence during the time interval when TID were observed.
- Col 7: Maximum PCN index (merging electric field indicator) during the hour preceding TID occurrence and, separated by a double slash, the range taken by PCN during TID occurrence. If no TID were detected the double slash is not preceded by a number and only the range of the index over the full event period is listed.
- Col 8: Maximum PCS index during the hour preceding TID occurrence and, separated by a double slash, the range taken by PCS during TID occurrence. If no TID were detected the double slash is not preceded by a number and only the range of the index over the full event period is listed. An asterisk indicates lack of data.
- Col 9: Indicator of hemispherically conjugate TID occurrence (Y=yes, N=no). In case only one hemisphere was sufficiently covered by observations this hemisphere is given in parentheses. In case of no TID detection this field remains empty.
- Col 10: Indicator of interhemispheric circulation of TID (Y=yes, N=no). In case only one hemisphere was sufficiently covered by observations this hemisphere is given in parentheses. In case of no TID detection this field remains empty.
- Col 11: Region of TID origin. H = TID originating at high latitudes and traveling equatorward; L = TID originating at low latitudes or in the vicinity of the equator and traveling poleward; H+L = TID originating at high and low latitudes during the same event period.

Date	DoY	TID [UT]	min SYM-H [nT] // main phase [UT]	IL [nT] min // Time (UT)	IU [nT] max // Time (UT)	PC-N [mV/m] at TID start // TID range	PC-S [mV/m] at TID start // TID range	conjugate (E) : Europe (A) : Africa	interhemisph (E) : Europe (A) : Africa	origin H : high lat L : low lat
2012-03-07	067	06 - 15	-100 nT // 04 - 07	-600 // 06.00	+600 // 13.30	6 // 1 - 9	6 // 0 - 8	Y	N	H + L
2012-03-08	068	13 - 17	recovery phase	-650 // 12.30	+700 // 15.30	10 // -2 - 10	3 // -2 - 10	Y	N	H + L
2012-03-09	069	06 - 14	-150 nT // 01 - 08	-1900 // 04.30	+700 // 14.00	12 // 0 - 20	10 // 0 - 16	(E)	(E)	H
2012-03-10	070	06 - 15	recovery phase	-550 // 05.30	+150 // 14.00	5 // 2 - 6	5 // 1 - 6	Y	N	H + L
2013-10-02	275	08 - 17	-90 nT // 02 - 06	-250 // 08.00	+150 // 11.30	2 // -1 - 3	4 // -1 - 5	Y	N	H + L
2014-02-19	050	03 - 18	-120 nT // 15 - 09(+1d)	-1300 // 05.00	+250 // 14.00	8 // -1 - 11	8 // -2 - 12	Y	N	H
2014-02-27	058	17 - 23	-100 nT // 17 - 23	-900 // 22.00	+400 // 17.30	4 // 1 - 8	5 // 2 - 8	(E)	(E)	H
2015-01-07	007	11 - 15	-150 nT // 07 - 11	-250 // 11.30	+600 // 11.30	6 // 0 - 7	5 // 3 - 8	Y	N	H + L
2015-01-21	021	* // *	storm-free	-300 // 18.00	+300 // 17.30					
2015-01-22	022	* // *	storm-free	-350 // 00.30	+200 // 18.30					
2015-02-17	048	06 - 18	-70 nT // 20(-1d) - 24	-500 // 22.00	+400 // 18.00	2 // -1 - 4	3 // -1 - 6	Y	N	L
2015-02-18	049	* // *	recovery phase	-600 // 21.00	+100 // 00.00					
2015-02-24	055	03 - 18	-70 nT // 01 - 03	-1250 // 03.30	+150 // 13.30	6 // 0 - 9	5 // 0 - 7	Y	N	H + L
2015-03-17	076	09 - 21	-230 nT // 05 - 23	-1400 // 17.30	+900 // 13.30	10 // -3 - 16	10 // -4 - 15	Y	Y	H + L
2015-06-22	173	19 - 24	-200 nT // 18 - 04(+1d)	-900 // 20.00	+600 // 16.30	9 // 5 - 18	9 // -5 - 25	Y	Y	H
2015-06-23	174	04 - 18	-200 nT // 18(-1d) - 04	-1500 // 04.00	+700 // 12.00	6 // -9 - 7	11 // -2 - 10	Y	Y	H + L
2015-10-12	285	06 - 21	recovery phase	-1300 // 17.00	+400 // 16.30	2 // 0 - 7	2 // 0 - 8	Y	N	H
2015-10-13	286	12 - 21	recovery phase	-950 // 21.00	+300 // 16.00	0 // 0 - 6	0 // 0 - 6	(A)	(A)	L
2015-11-03	307	03 - 07	-60 nT // 08 - 10	-800 // 18.30	+400 // 14.00	2 // 0 - 2	2 // 0 - 2	Y	N	L
2016-01-20	020	12 - 15	-100 nT // 03 - 17	-200 // 15.30	+600 // 16.00	2 // 2 - 3	3 // 3 - 5	Y	N	H
2016-10-12	286	* // *	ssc // 22	-280 // 21.00	+70 // 22.30					
2016-10-13	287	12 - 15	-120 nT // 22(-1d) - 24	-830 // 16.00	+630 // 17.00	3 // 3 - 8	3 // 3 - 8	(E)	(E)	H

Table 1: TID event periods with specific characteristics (see text on preceding page)

Date	DoY	TID [UT]	min SYM-H [nT] main phase [UT]	IL [nT] min // Time (UT)	IU [nT] max // Time (UT)	PC-N [mV/m] at TID start // TID range	PC-S [mV/m] at TID start // TID range	conjugate (E) : Europe (A) : Africa	interhemisph (E) : Europe (A) : Africa	origin H : high lat L : lowlat
2017-01-07	007	08 - 18	storm-free	-1000 // 18.00	+250 // 08.00	2 // 0 - 3	2 // 0 - 5	Y	N	H
2017-03-01	060	11 - 15	-70 nT // 07 - 22	-350 // 10.30	+350 // 13.30	6 // 1 - 7	**	Y	N	H
2017-03-27	086	12 - 18	-80 nT // 21(-1d) - 16	-200 // 12.00	+600 // 16.30	4 // 0 - 7	5 // 1 - 9	Y	Y	H
2017-04-21	111	13 - 24	-40 nT // 16 - 21	-850 // 19.30	+250 // 16.30	3 // 0 - 6	3 // -1 - 7	Y	N	H
2017-04-22	112	**	recovery phase	-1000 // 04.30	+300 // 02.00					
2017-07-16	197	12 - 17	-60 nT // 06 - 16	-850 // 10.00	+800 // 13.30	8 // -4 - 9	10 // 0 - 10	(A)	(A)	H
2017-08-31	243	**	-60 nT // 07 - 12	-350 // 08.30	+400 // 09.00					
2017-09-07	250	12 - 18	-120 nT // 20 - 01(+1d)	-400 // 10.00	+200 // 15.00	4 // -4 - 4	6 // -2 - 6	(A)	(A)	H
2017-09-08	251	10 - 17	-100 nT // 11 - 18	-3700 // 00.30	+1000 // 14.00	0 // -1 - 12	3 // 0 - 17	Y	N	H
2017-09-09	252	**	recovery phase	-400 // 01.30	+100 // 01.00					
2017-09-10	253	**	recovery phase	-550 // 23.00	+150 // 16.30					
2017-09-27	270	03 - 19	-70 // 07 - 06(+1d)	-200 // 12.30	+300 // 14.30	2 // -1 - 2	3 // 0 - 3	Y	N	H + L
2017-10-13	286	**	storm-free	-1400 // 19.00	+800 // 14.30					
2017-11-07	311	**	-90 nT // 04 - 04(+1d)	-1100 // 19.00	+450 // 18.00					
2017-11-20	324	**	-60 nT // 17 - 07(+1d)	-800 // 24.00	+200 // 19.00					
2017-11-21	325	**	-60 nT // 17(-1d) - 07	-750 // 00.30	+150 // 09.00					

Table 1 continued

4.2 Evaluation of the event collection

The following conclusions can be drawn from the information contained in Table 1.

- (1) 38 event periods were analysed most of which occurred during geomagnetic storms. LSTID were detected in at least one hemisphere in 26 of them.
- (2) 4 out of the remaining 12 event periods fell on moderate or weak storms (SYM-H not exceeding -90 nT) and 8 occurred late in the recovery phase of a storm or during storm-free intervals.
- (3) No period was found during which LSTID were observed in one hemisphere and could definitely be excluded to have occurred in the other hemisphere. If sufficient data coverage existed for both hemispheres (which was the case for 20 event periods) conjugate TID occurred were seen without exception.
- (4) During or immediately after the main phase of a geomagnetic storm LSTID were detected in at least one hemisphere and in case of sufficient data coverage in both hemispheres.
- (5) During the event periods 2017-08-31, 2017-11-07, 2017-11-20, 2017-11-21 data coverage data extended only over a narrow latitude range, insufficient to determine whether observed TEC variations were indeed traveling. These four are among the eight noted in (2).
- (6) In the late storm recovery phase, during storm-free intervals, and prior to the onset of a storm main phase LSTID were detected in at least one hemisphere in only 4 out of 13 qualifying event periods.
- (7) If sufficient data coverage existed for both hemispheres interhemispheric circulation was observed in only 4 out of 20 event periods. In no case a constructive interference at the equatorial crossing point was identified which could have led to a local amplitude enhancement.
- (8) LSTID were observed to be traveling only equatorward during 14 event periods, poleward during 3 event period, and concurrently equatorward and poleward during 9 event periods.
- (9) The magnitude of the global SYM-H index, the local auroral electrojet indices IL and IU, and of the Polar Cap indices PCN and PCS played only a minor role. The three event periods with interhemispheric circulation (2015-03-17, 2015-06-22, 2015-11-03) occurred during weak and strong storms, moderate and strong auroral electrojet intensities, and small and large PC indices, respectively.

5. Recommendations

Our conclusions, based on the event table presented in the previous section, lead to the following recommendations.

- (1) During geomagnetic storms, even if of moderate magnitude (SYM-H between 50 and 100 nT), the likeliness that LSTID are launched is very high. They should be expected to be launched at auroral latitudes in both hemispheres and at equatorial latitudes and are likely to propagate equatorward and poleward, respectively.
- (2) If LSTID are launched in one hemisphere during the main or recovery phases of a geomagnetic storm it is almost certain that LSTID are also launched in the other hemisphere.
- (3) Among all LSTID observed to be conjugate in both hemispheres we found that only a minority (15%) propagates into the opposite hemisphere.
- (4) We did not detect any case of TID launched concurrently in both hemispheres and propagating equatorward thereby experiencing constructive interference and amplitude enhancement when crossing each other.
- (5) We conclude that interhemispheric circulation exists but is not a significant threat to operators otherwise affected by TID.

Space weather service operators which become aware of LSTID associated with geomagnetic storms propagating equatorward or poleward in one hemisphere should consider that it is very likely to experience them also in the other hemisphere.

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